

Literature Research on the Use of Educational Facilities under the Responsibility of the School Principal

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Abstract

The roles that various pieces of training equipment serve might help categorize them. These are many educational resources, including learning tools, teaching aids, and learning settings. There are two distinct categories that may be applied to educational establishments. First, the classroom, the library, the practice room, and the laboratory are the types of spaces that are directly used in the process of teaching and learning. Second, there is the infrastructure that is not directly used in the teaching and learning process but does in some way assist the learning process. Some examples of this kind of infrastructure are the office room, the principal's room, the teachers' room, the restrooms, and the school canteen. An integrated strategy to preserving, enhancing, and changing an organization's facilities to produce an environment that strongly supports an organization's key objectives, as stated by Peter Barrett and David Baldry (2004: xiii). It should be obvious from the description that essential components of facilities management are considered as an integrative function, in which management concerns take precedence over technical difficulties; and a justified and directed service to make a positive contribution to the core business. In other words, management matters take precedence. How vital is it that educational facilities be managed effectively? According to a report published by the OECD in 2001, "Excellence in educational facilities lies not only in the quality of design and construction but also in the quality of management." PEB 101 (Training Building Programme) has concentrated its emphasis on four

concerns over the last five years: maintenance, space utilization, economics, and health and safety. Facility management involves a number of interconnected factors. We are able to draw the conclusion that educational facilities are any and all structures, regardless of whether or not they are movable, that are required in the process of teaching and learning and that may either directly or indirectly impact the goals of education. It is a difficult process because it has to be adequately integrated with national development plans, as well as plans for regional and local levels of development. The task of planning the demands of educational facilities. Planning is a kind of planning that incorporates the planning of a development into its overall structure.

Keywords: *Use of Educational Facilities, Educational Facilities, Responsibility of the School Principal, Educational Administration, Manager in Educational Administration*

Introduction

The sort of training programs and the objectives that are established will determine the requirements for the development of the training facility. The process of purchasing new facilities is strongly connected to the planning of training. It is essential to conduct a thorough examination to determine which components call for specific instruments or supplies. As a result of this study, the tool or pieces of equipment that are required may be documented. Either the primary or the deputy director may carry out these duties. There are several different avenues open to buyers interested in purchasing educational institutions. There are a variety of methods available for acquiring land, including buying, bartering, granting, purchasing, and accepting tenure. Making, purchasing, renting, or renting to own, getting grants, or swapping structures are all viable options for financing the acquisition of a building. The purchasing process allows for the acquisition of equipment as well as furnishings. You may buy furniture either finished or unfinished, depending on your preference. The acquisition of equipment may either be done on one's own accord or with assistance from governmental agencies, private groups, communities, people, etc., depending on the situation. It is important to take into account the requirements of the pupils while planning and preparing to make purchases of furniture and educational equipment. The school is responsible for selecting and acquiring furniture and equipment that is appropriate for its instructional program as well as the ages, interests, and degrees of physical and psychological development of its pupils. Endang Herawan and Sukarti According to Nasihin (2002:118), there are prerequisites that must be met before purchasing any furniture or equipment.

- 1) Suitable for students' activities in teaching and learning activities

- 2) Strong, easy to maintain and easy to clean
- 3) Has a simple basic pattern
- 4) Flexible, hence easy to use.

C. Furniture construction:

- 1) strong and durable
- 2) Solid and easy to make
- 3) Materials should be readily available on the market and adaptable to local conditions.

The raw materials should be sturdy while yet being lightweight and should not put the pupils' safety in jeopardy. Because of this, the chances that are presented to the students need to be appropriate and favorable to the students' educational ideals, as well as their physical and mental state. The principal of the school is the one who is in charge of making decisions on the usage of educational facilities. It is essential to have managers who are assigned the job of planning the program and who oversee an area that is typical of a training facility or staff members who are affiliated with transport facilities in order to regulate these activities.

The facility is intended to facilitate various learning and teaching endeavors. The state of these goods will not remain unchanged over time, but instead will deteriorate to the point that they are no longer usable or may possibly become extinct. The infrastructure of educational institutions is not readily damaged or destroyed; nonetheless, businesses need regular user maintenance. Maintenance is an activity in which the purchase expenses are included in the overall school budget and are set aside for the continuance of the building, equipment, and furniture, including the interest cost provision for repairing, restoring, and renovating. This is done as part of the overall school budget.

As a consequence of this, it is anticipated that the future supply of teachers would be impacted, given that a proportionately higher number of instructors reach the age of retirement each year. In addition, in recent years, the profession as a whole has lost a substantial amount of its appeal, especially from a financial one. This is particularly the case with regard to financial remuneration. Other statistics indicate that, in at least some countries, a sizeable component of the teaching workforce does not carry a standard teaching license, and the percentage of 'out-of-field' teaching assignments is shockingly high in fundamental subject areas. This is despite the fact that the majority of nations have a standard teaching license. This is the case despite the fact that some nations have licensing standards that are more stringent than others. In light of these new developments, it seems that there is more than sufficient rationale for doing research into what

would be the most effective strategies for managing both the supply and demand of academics. Because of the success of this research, we were able to find some empirical data, which assisted us in developing a complete set of policies that need significant consideration in order to manage teacher supply and demand. There was sufficient evidence gathered that it could be included in the report.

Methodology

It is noticeable that the policy instruments employed on the demand side appear to have far less promise in improving student results than the policy tools used on the supply side or in the structure of schooling marketplaces. This is one of the conclusions drawn from the research presented here. This conclusion is significant because it indicates how crucial it is to concentrate on the supply side of the education market or the structure of education market structures. To be more precise, recent research suggests that the effect of reducing the universal class size, which is the key policy instrument on the demand side, is low and exceedingly expensive. This is because of the fact that it is the primary policy instrument on the demand side. There is a growing body of support for the concept that individuals who stand to gain the most from efforts to reduce class sizes should be the focus of such efforts. Reducing the number of students in a class may be helpful in some circumstances (for example, at lower grade levels or for children with lower incomes and greater disadvantages), but doing so on a wide scale is prohibitively costly. As a result, efforts to reduce class sizes should be directed toward the pupils who stand to gain the most from doing so. There is a general agreement. It has come to our attention that supply-side policies (for example, policies that increase the attractiveness of the teaching profession) and their impact on the structure of education markets (for example, policies that decentralize decision-making) hold greater promise for improving the quality of teaching. This is because supply-side policies aim to increase the number of people entering the teaching profession.

It is clear that those who are interested in teaching, those who are now teaching, and those who have previously taught are influenced by incentives. This is true for both present educators and those who have had teaching positions in the past. Factors such as salary and opportunity costs play a big role in determining who decides to enter the teaching profession, who continues working in the field, and who decides to come back to teaching after taking a hiatus. Other factors, such as career opportunities in a teaching career, working circumstances, teacher training and certification procedures, and the image of the profession all play an enormously significant part in the decisions that potential trainers make when recruiting the instructors, they wish to employ. In addition, a

number of pieces of evidence point to the fact that a person's personality qualities play a crucial part in determining the degree to which they are influenced by financial rewards. When a teacher is in their first few years of a teaching career, they have a higher rate of quitting the profession than at any other stage in their career. Teachers who are more academically proficient and who work in professions that give more possibilities outside of education are more likely to quit the profession and less likely to return to the classroom if they do leave it. This is especially true for teachers who have worked in disciplines that offer more options outside of education. It is anticipated that this pattern will go on. One further essential aspect is that male and female beneficiaries of incentives react differently to the benefits they get. In view of the critical relevance of these data, consideration should be given to how best to incorporate them into the policymaking process.

Finding incentives that will eliminate from the pool those individuals who do not possess the abilities necessary to become teachers, attract suitable candidates and past educators to a pool of aspiring teachers, and retain exceptional quality trainers who are already working in the profession is a difficulty that must be overcome in order to create effective policies. In order for education administrators to be successful in reaching this aim, they need to devise an incentive structure that will turn the teaching profession into a workforce that has the requisite distribution of experience and ability. For instance, given the higher dropout rates for young and elite teachers, the wage structure should try to decrease teacher attrition in the early years of teachers' employment. This is because the dropout rates for young and elite teachers are greater. It is important for the incentive system to take into consideration the reality that women often quit their careers for reasons that are associated with raising families. This is of utmost significance in light of the fact that the employment of women is necessary for the continued existence of a workforce in the teaching profession. For this reason, it would be advantageous to enhance the "flexibility" of the profession by offering services like as daycare, or by making the job itself more flexible. 6) In a similar vein, the preparation of educators and their subsequent certification is an essential component of the bigger picture. Aspiring educators want incentives to participate in high-quality education, and it would be ideal to set licensing standards that dissuade persons who do not possess the abilities necessary for teaching effectively. It is necessary to provide trainee educators with incentives in order to encourage their participation in high-quality education. More stringent conditions for admittance into programs that educate teachers, a greater focus on academic rigor in the curriculum, and certification requirements that include examinations of core skills and expertise in particular areas are all possible directions that reform in this area may take. In addition to these steps, the standards for obtaining licenses might be loosened for those who have promise

in other disciplines. In a similar vein, professional development has been identified as an essential resource that may give possibilities for more experienced trainers to learn new abilities. This is because professional development can help trainers acquire new talents. Due to the fact that it is able to supply possibilities of this kind, it should therefore be used as an essential component in various retention techniques. In addition, a plethora of studies highlight the fact that it is desirable to make an effort to enhance the image of the teaching profession in society and highlight the fact that this is something that should be worked on. It is in everyone's best interest to make an effort to enhance the image of teaching as a profession in society. In order to do this, schools would need to be given greater autonomy, and teachers will need to be given more authority in the classroom.

The findings of this study shed light on the issue of the rising relevance of school organization, which is one that has garnered a lot of attention as of late. It has been shown that the organizational circumstances of schools have an effect on the turnover rate of teachers, and that performance-based accountability systems can be a suitable option for those looking to enhance the results of education. Those who are responsible for formulating public policy are increasingly speaking out about the need of decentralizing decision-making. The first idea is that schools need to be granted a greater degree of independence in the management of problems such as the formulation of their own recruiting and recruitment techniques, the definition of remuneration levels, incentive structure, assessment methods, and investment in continuing education. Specifically, policies that contribute to improving recruitment processes are particularly significant because they highlight the link between pay plans and the quality of instructors. This is why it is necessary to have policies that contribute to improving recruiting processes. When it comes to establishing a connection between teacher pay and teacher quality, the research that is provided in this article demonstrates that recruiting strategies may sometimes be rather ineffective.

Therefore, in order for schools to make progress in terms of attracting and keeping higher quality teachers, it is probable that they will need to introduce stronger performance incentives for school employees. This is due to an increase in the level of competition that exists for high-quality teaching positions. This may be one of the steps included in a larger package of reforms with the goal of introducing more elements of competition into the educational system. In addition to the introduction of productivity-based incentives and increased autonomy in the management of schools, these elements may include a wider choice of schools, wage differentiation to account for deficiencies in certain subject areas, grade levels, or regions of the country, and schools that compete directly with each other for teachers. Additionally, these elements may include schools that compete directly with each other for students. In this environment, the structure of careers

may include remuneration that is driven by market forces, responsibility that is based on performance, a variety of career routes, and continual chances for practical professional growth.

Literature Review

It is general known that incentives play a significant part in achieving outcomes in a variety of contexts, including educational environments and other aspects of daily life. And in the context of the management of teacher supply and demand, education policy looks to be heading towards disorderly behaviors, with a concentration on a set of incentive-based processes. This is concerning. This stands in stark contrast to the circumstances that prevailed in the 1980s and 1990s, a time period during which education policy was subject to stringent regulation. In this approach, policymakers underline how crucial it is to explicitly correlate such incentive schemes with the achievement of students. This should be the ultimate objective of any education system.

In addition, this article sheds light on the OECD's present data availability as well as the necessary data needs for future quantitative research. It is necessary to have access to trustworthy data in order to accurately assess the teaching staff that is presently in existence as well as to design policies that will enhance educational institutions. For instance, despite the common sense that certain countries are hampered by a scarcity of qualified teachers, there is inadequate actual evidence on the particular reasons and degree of these problems. This is despite the fact that there is a popular notion that some countries are affected by a shortage of qualified instructors. The areas that are best covered by the data that is presently available are the demographic profile of teachers, demand-side characteristics (such as student enrollment, composition of the school-age population, needed teaching time for students, instructors' teaching loads and enrollment rates), and teacher compensation. Specifically, the demographic profile of teachers includes information such as these.

In addition, the study reveals that there are certain gaps in the data. To begin, there is a dearth of data, if any at all, on people's entrance into and leave from the field. The following items of data are not currently available: attrition and retention rates, characteristics of people leaving, reasons for leaving/entering/re-entering the profession, reasons for job dissatisfaction, potential supply of recent graduates, potential supply of returning, and percentage of newly certified teachers entering the profession. Second, it would seem that no data have been gathered about the outcomes of the procedures that are used to choose instructors. These types of data include, for instance, the number of openings that were deemed "difficult to fill," the percentage of positions

that were filled by instructors who possessed "emergency certification," the proportion of assignments that were deemed "out of field," and the processes that were utilized to fill openings that were deemed "difficult to fill." may contain. In addition, essential components of the teaching strength profile, such as the proportion of unqualified instructors working in the teaching sector and the current state of teacher licenses, are difficult to acquire. This is a problem. Some of the other important data gaps that exist include information on teacher education, teacher certification, the existence of market mechanisms, teacher recruitment practices, the organizational structure of schools, professional development activities, teaching and learning practices, standards and assessment practices, and partnerships.

Argument

They combine a learning environment, several educational resources, and pedagogical aids into a single package. There are two distinct classifications that are able to be applied to various types of educational institutions. To begin, the areas of the building that are directly used for the process of teaching and learning include spaces such as classrooms, libraries, practice rooms, and labs. Second, there is the infrastructure that is not directly engaged in the teaching and learning process but helps it in some manner, such as the office room, the office of the principal, the staff room, the restrooms, and the school canteens. It is an integrated strategy to preserving, upgrading, and changing an organization's facilities in order to produce an environment that strongly supports an organization's key objectives, as stated by Peter Barrett and David Baldry. It ought to be obvious from the definition that the most essential aspects of facilities management are regarded to be an integrative role in which management considerations take precedence over technical concerns; and that it is essential for a justifiable service to make a positive contribution to the main company. This should be the case given that the definition focuses on the key work responsibilities.

What role does management play in the operation of educational facilities? According to a statement that was released by the OECD in the year 2001, "Excellence in educational facilities lies not only in the quality of design and construction, but also in the quality of management." It is feasible to draw the conclusion that educational facilities include all of the required facilities in the process of teaching and learning, regardless of whether or not they are movable. These facilities may either directly or indirectly impact the goals of education. According to the Teaching Building Programme, the four areas of maintenance, land use, finances, and health and safety have received the greatest focus during the last five years.

It is not an easy job to plan the needs for the purchase of educational facilities since they need to be closely connected to both national development plans and growth plans at the regional

and local levels. The process of incorporating a planning system and the planning of a specific development into one another is referred to as planning. The sorts of educational programs and learning goals that are pursued each have their own unique set of planning criteria for educational buildings. The process of putting together a training plan is inextricably intertwined with the purchase of new facilities. The facilities were brought online when the needs assessment for them had been finished and then completed. One of the possible courses of action is to do an analysis to identify whether department need more tools or equipment. Depending on the findings of this research, a patented device may be developed, or it may establish what kind of machinery is necessary. This duty might be carried out by either the principal or the assistant principal. It is possible to go to the educational institutions in a variety of various methods. Acquiring land may be accomplished via a variety of means, including purchasing, obtaining grants, accepting the right to use, or bartering. The acquisition of a building may be performed in a number of ways, including the construction of a new structure, the purchase of an existing building, the renting of an existing building, the receipt of a grant, or the replacement of existing buildings. One of the available choices for acquiring goods like furniture and other pieces of equipment is to make a purchase. You may purchase furniture that has already been constructed, or you can buy it from people who are still working on it. It is possible to acquire the essential equipment via self-help, with the assistance of governmental agencies, commercial groups, communities, and individuals, or through any combination of the aforementioned options. The demands of the pupils should be taken into consideration throughout the planning and preparation stages of the procurement of educational furniture and equipment. It is essential to take responsibility for choosing and supplying the school with furniture and other equipment that is suitable for the curriculum, as well as the ages of the students, their hobbies, and the degree to which they have developed physically and psychologically.

Endang Herawan and Sukarti According to Nasihin (2002: 118), there are several requirements that need to be satisfied before the manufacturing of furniture and other equipment can begin. Program writing has been given to managers who supervise a facility that is special to the education sector or to professionals who are involved in the administration of the facilities in order to make these activities operate more smoothly. Particularly pertinent to the usage of the facility are the following factors:

- 1. It is strongly recommended not to draft the usage plan at the same time as other groups.*
- 2. Great emphasis should be placed on activities at the school's principal level.*

3. *At the beginning of the current academic year, a usage hour or schedule must be submitted.*
4. *Laboratory assistants, librarians, computer operators, etc. It is important to employ suitable employees with competence in the field.*
5. *To create the usage program of the facility, taking into account both compulsory and optional activities.*

The facility was designed with the intention of making activities linked to education more accessible. The status of these things will not improve over time; rather, it will deteriorate worse, eventually leading to their annihilation and maybe even their extinction. However, commercial properties need more frequent and in-depth upkeep than educational ones since they are more susceptible to being vandalized or destroyed. Purchasing costs are included into the overall budget for the school since maintenance is an activity that requires funding. This finance is set aside for the maintenance of the building, the equipment, and the furnishings. Additionally, there is a provision for the interest cost of any repairs, restorations, or replacements that may be necessary.

In addition to expanding, one's knowledge and skill set, there should be a strong emphasis placed on cultivating appropriate habits and attitudes that may be applied to one's financial situation. People's awareness of how to effectively manage their money throughout their life, as well as their abilities and confidence, may be improved via the use of financial education, whose primary objective is to that end. It is very necessary for initiatives pertaining to financial education to have a distinct focus not only on information and abilities but also on attitudes and actions. This is due to the fact that doing so is essential. If people are given the information and skills they need to succeed, but they still choose not to use them, then not much will be accomplished despite the provision of those resources.

Supporting Teachers

Teachers need to either run the programs for financial education themselves or be actively engaged in the program's management if it is run by someone other than the teachers. The delivery of programs for financial education in the classroom may benefit from the participation of outside specialists. Either educators need to teach the financial education programs themselves or they need to be actively engaged in the program even if it is being taught by someone else. However, it is also conceivable that they may not have the requisite abilities to teach financial education in a

classroom environment, while having important technical knowledge and first-hand expertise on the topic. This is a possibility even if it is less likely. It is probable that a student will benefit the most from their financial education, regardless of whether it is provided by instructors or by an outsider, if the teacher is there and clearly active in the process.

For students to benefit from financial education, their instructors (or other providers) must possess the knowledge, skills, and self-assurance required to impart it in an effective manner. Both in the context of the initial teacher education that they get and in the context of their ongoing professional development, effective arrangements should be developed to offer training for teachers. It is necessary for instructors (or other providers) to be competent in the subject of financial education for the program to be successful. Initial teacher education programs should provide training for those who will be instructing topics that are relevant. Having said that, this by itself will not be sufficient to remedy the issue.

Training is also necessary for current teachers:

Many do not include financial education as part of their initial teacher education; and even those with relevant initial teacher education can benefit from occasional refresher courses, including giving them the opportunity to learn about new techniques and methods for delivering financial education.

Training should be offered for both newly hired teachers and those who are already in the profession. There are times when there are no "correct" answers, and instructors need to have the courage to discuss challenging issues with their kids, particularly ones that involve money. One such topic is bullying. It is unreasonable to think that the majority of educators will have the time, knowledge, or motivation to investigate the resources and technologies that will provide the most beneficial assistance for financial education projects. It is essential for educators to have easy access to a variety of resources and tools in order to effectively provide a financial education to their students. Instead, there need to be one definitive resource (or a restricted number, if there are more than one) as well as technologies that are accessible to instructors. This information may serve as a clearinghouse for other information. It is essential that trainers be made aware of the location(s) of the source(s) of assistance in order for them to be able to seek assistance when it is required. The instructional materials and tools that teachers utilize should be of a high quality, should be effective, and should be free from any kind of commercial or other bias. The resource should be properly structured and provide clear instructions so that instructors may readily locate

information and resources that are suitable for the teacher's intended purpose (for example, the age group that is being educated about financial matters). Plans need to be put in place, maybe in the form of a well-recognized accrediting system, that will allow educators to identify materials and tools that are of a higher standard than those already available.

If an organization is thinking about producing new materials or tools, they should first assess whether or not they could utilize or modify materials and tools that have previously been developed, either in their own nation or in another country elsewhere in the globe. There are many different instances of high-quality materials and technology that might act as models for new ventures to begin. Those who want to contribute to programs aimed at improving financial education often produce fresh resources in some way. However, if there is not a thorough investigation of what is now available, there is a risk of producing a new version of materials or tools that are already available, and this new version may be of worse quality than the existing one. Even if there is an examination of what currently exists, there is still the possibility of this danger occurring. For instructors and those who work in this industry, the abundance of tools and technologies that are designed to deliver essentially the same answers may be more perplexing than useful. This is particularly important to keep in mind when there are a number of different teachers working in the same class.

As a consequence of this, organizations who are exploring the development of new materials or tools should first consult with national experts in order to have a better understanding of the possible gaps that may exist in the present proposal. In addition, national experts should investigate what has been developed in other nations and assess if it would be more effective and efficient to adapt or adopt one or more of these based on getting the required licenses as opposed to commissioning the creation of new materials or tools. This should be done before deciding whether it would be more effective and efficient to produce new materials or instruments. It is important to keep in mind that in order to legally carry out this activity, the necessary licenses will need to be acquired. Acknowledgment of achievements

Establishing learning goals and keeping track of student progress should be priorities. It is important that the learning outcomes be set in such a manner that there is no room for ambiguity on the objectives that the financial education program intends to accomplish. It is vital to measure the development of students for two reasons: first, so that the efficiency of the different aspects of the program can be reviewed, and modifications may be made, if required; and second, since it is crucial for students to be motivated by results. Measuring the success of students is important.

Motivating factors for students, instructors, and educational institutions sometimes include the receipt of prizes or other kinds of acknowledgment in appreciation of exceptional accomplishments. Qualifications are examples of this form of acknowledgment that may be given. Both individual accomplishment and high-quality financial education programs should be recognized in some way, whether via the establishment of prizes or other types of acknowledgment (such as qualifying), which should be given some thought. In the case of students, this may take the shape of credentials or certificates attesting to their level of accomplishment. Awards (including those that symbolize comparison with other schools) and certificates that may be based on self-assessment are two examples that may be included in this category for educators or educational institutions. Other possible inclusions include accreditation. If students are given the opportunity to pursue studies leading to a certificate, it is possible that their parents, teachers, and other adults in their lives may be encouraged to enroll them in financial education programs.

This is due to the fact that they are able to get physical recognition of their accomplishments. Colleges that provide courses in financial education may play a role in fostering the development of individuals who have a wide range of useful skills and knowledge. Students enrolled in various programs at universities and colleges have to be encouraged to take use of the financial education help and courses that are available via these institutions. On the other hand, because of the structure of these classes, it is more probable that they will be appealing to those who have the goal of pursuing a profession that is connected to financial services. Therefore, educational institutions such as universities and colleges should be encouraged to give their students well-planned and coherent financial education programs that may include short courses and are led by student support services. These programs should be offered to the students of the educational institutions' respective students. All students, irrespective of the fields in which they major, need to be eligible to participate in these activities.

Evaluations of financial education programs should be carried out with a high degree of scrutiny in order to get a better understanding of the most effective methods in which financial education may be given in a range of situations. The goal of this knowledge is to improve the quality of the financial education that can be provided. Evaluation of financial education programs is necessary in order to allow successful programs to be expanded upon and copied in other locations, and unsuccessful programs to be either replaced or discontinued. This evaluation will also contribute to the production of evidence that may assist in convincing policymakers and education decision makers about the implementation of financial education in schools. It is quite probable, at the very least in part, that the approach that is used to assess a program will depend on being both inexpensive and practical. For instance, there is no guarantee that one will be able

to conduct a longitudinal evaluation. The development of a standardized framework that is versatile enough to be either a straightforward and low-cost procedure or a more involved endeavor, depending on the particulars of the circumstance, is one approach that may be pursued. Because the goal of financial education is to teach individuals how to better manage their money by increasing their knowledge, improving their abilities, and increasing their self-confidence, assessments should consider how programs affect participants' attitudes and behaviors in addition to how they affect participants' knowledge, skills, and abilities. This is because the purpose of financial education is to teach individuals how to better manage their money by increasing their knowledge, improving their abilities, and increasing their self-confidence. Global coordination 18. The provision of a financial education for pupils is still in its formative stages in a lot of different nations.

It is important to promote collaboration, which should include the use of the 117th Working Group of the OECD as an international venue for the sharing of information and research on national experiences, as well as international best practices and standards. In these nations, experienced professionals have a lot to learn from the expertise that their peers in countries that have achieved more progress in their development can share with them. Additionally, specialists in nations that have achieved considerable success may benefit from knowing about the progress made in other nations. This is because such nations may have been inspired to continue their own efforts. Within the framework of the Financial Education Project, the OECD is in a position that is well suited to act as a facilitator for the sharing of information and experience. This goal may be attained via a number of means, such as through the newly introduced worldwide Gateway for Financial Education, the formulation of worldwide principles and standards of good behavior, publications, and conferences (Shaun Mundy, 2008).

Educational Public Relations

Upon completion of this section, students should be able to:

1. To give an explanation of what the term "educational public relations" means.
2. To outline the many forms that educational public relations can take.
3. To give some examples of how the school and the community can work together.

Increasing public awareness and acceptance is one of the goals of educational public relations, which is a function of strategic management in the manner in which communication is

carried out. Companies need to make sure that they develop harmonious connections with the communities that surround them as part of the process of getting public acceptance. This may be accomplished by sticking to values such as being open, honest, fair, and consistent, as well as ensuring that they do not isolate themselves. (Kasali, 2005: 15) In James E. Grunig's (2011: 1) description of the excellence theory of public relations, the value of public relations for businesses and society is based on the social responsibility of management actions and the quality of connections with stakeholder publics. In other words, the value of public relations is determined by the social responsibility of management actions and the quality of connections with stakeholder publics. Kasali (2005:15) makes reference to this hypothesis in their work. The idea behind this concept is that in order for an organization to be successful, its stakeholders need to behave in a manner that not only meets the objectives that they have established for the business but also finds solutions to the challenges that they are now facing. When we acknowledge that schools are public institutions, the justification for creating and maintaining a public relations program in schools, particularly public schools, becomes abundantly evident. Since public schools are democratic organizations that are owned by the people, it is especially crucial for public schools to establish and execute a public relations campaign. It is only reasonable that local citizens, whose tax funds are used to pay for public schools, should have access to information about these institutions and the ability to take part in the administration of them (Lee Stewart, 2007).

Conclusion

Increasing public awareness and acceptance is one of the goals of educational public relations, which is a function of strategic management in the manner in which communication is carried out. Companies need to make sure that they develop harmonious connections with the communities that surround them as part of the process of getting public acceptance. This may be accomplished by sticking to values such as being open, honest, fair, and consistent, as well as ensuring that they do not isolate themselves. (Kasali, 2005: 15) In James E. Grunig's (2011: 1) description of the excellence theory of public relations, the value of public relations for businesses and society is based on the social responsibility of management actions and the quality of connections with stakeholder publics. In other words, the value of public relations is determined by the social responsibility of management actions and the quality of connections with stakeholder publics. Kasali (2005:15) makes reference to this hypothesis in their work. The idea behind this concept is that in order for an organization to be successful, its stakeholders need to behave in a manner that not only meets the objectives that they have established for the business but also finds

solutions to the challenges that they are now facing. When we acknowledge that schools are public institutions, the justification for creating and maintaining a public relations program in schools, particularly public schools, becomes abundantly evident. Since public schools are democratic organizations that are owned by the people, it is especially crucial for public schools to establish and execute a public relations campaign. It is only reasonable that local citizens, whose tax funds are used to pay for public schools, should have access to information about these institutions and the ability to take part in the administration of them (Lee Stewart, 2007).

References

- Ahmed, R. Effects of Online Education on Encoding and Decoding Process of Students and Teachers . In Proceedings of the International Association for Development of the Information Society , International Conference on e-Learning, Madrid, Spain , 17–19 July 2018.
- Betts , K. Lost in translation : Importance of effective communication in online education . Online J. Distance learnadm . 2009, 12, 1–14.
- Bhatti, MT; Teevno, RA Nonverbal Communication (NVC) and teacher presence in collaborative online learning. J. Contemp . Issues bus . Gov. 2021, 27, 308–316.
- Hair , JF, Jr .; Hult , GTM; Ringle, CM; Sarstedt , M. A. Primer on Partial Least squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), 3rd ed.; Sage : Thousand Oaks , CA, USA, 2021.
- Hart, C Factors associated with students persistence in an online program of study : A review of the literature _ J Interact . Learn Online . 2012, 11, 19–42.
- Henseler , J.; Ringle, CM; Sarstedt , M.A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling . J Acad . Mark. sci . 2015, 43, 115–135. [green version]
- Hinton , P.; McMurray , I.; Brownlow , C. SPSS Explained , 2nd ed.; Routledge : London , UK, 2014.
- Hu, LT; Bentler, PM Fit indices in covariance structure modeling : Sensitivity to underparameterized model misspecification . psycho _ Methods 1998, 3, 424–453.

- Hulland , J. Use of partials least squares (PLS) in strategic management research : A review of four recent studies . *strategy _ manag _ J.* 1999, 20, 195–204.
- Kock , N.; Hadaya , P. Minimum sample size estimation in PLS-SEM: The inverse square root and gamma- exponential methods . *Inf . syst . J.* 2018, 28, 227–261.
- Li , M., Zhu, J., and Wang, L. (2022). classroom teaching performance evaluation model guided by big data and mobile computing . *Wireless Commun . MobileComputer . _* :2022. doi : 10.1155/2022/2084423
- Li , X., and Sun, X. (2018). interface design and development of coating materials in lithium – sulfur batteries . *Adv . funct . mater.* 28:1801323. doi : 10.1002/adfm.201801323
- Lin, SS, Shen , SL, Zhou, A., and Xu, YS (2021). Risk assessment and management of excavation system based on fuzzy set theory and machine learning methods . *autom . Constr .* 122:103490. doi : 10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103490
- Lu, H., Zhang, Y., Li , Y., Jiang, C., and Abbas, H. (2020). User- oriented virtual mobile network resource management for vehicle communications . *IEEE Trans. Intel . trans . syst .* 22, 3521–3532. doi : 10.1109/TITS.2020.2991766
- Matos Pedro, E., Alves , H., and Leitão , J. (2020). In search of intangible connections : intellectual capital , performance and quality of life in higher education institutions _ *high. educ _* 83, 243–260. doi: 10.1007/s10734-020-00653-9
- Mosleh , SM; Kasasbeha , MA; Aljawarneh , YM; Alrimawi , I.; Saifan , AR The impact of online teaching on stress and burnout of academics during the transition to remote teaching from home . *BMC Med . educ _* 2022, 22, 475.
- Pastor , J.M.; Peraita , C.; Serrano , L.; Soler , A. high education institutions , economics growth and GDP per capita in European Union countries . *EUR. Plan. stud _* 2018, 26, 1616–1637.
- Ringle, CM; Wende , S.; Becker, JM *SmartPLS 4.* Boenningstedt : SmartPLS GmbH. 2015. Available online: <http://www.smartpls.com> (accessed on 6 November 2022).
- Ringle, M. HTMT Discriminant Validity . *Forum SmartPLS .* Available online: <https://forum.smartpls.com/viewtopic.php?t=3616> (accessed on 9 January 2023).

Wang, C.-M.; Reeves , T. C. The Meaning of Culture in Online Education : Implications for Teaching , Learning and Design. In Globalized E-Learning Cultural Challenges ; Edmundson , A., Ed.; IGI Global: Hershey , PA, USA, 2007; pp . 1–17.

Yana, AGA; Rusdhi , HA; Wibowo , MA Analysis of factors affecting design changes in construction project with partial Least Square (PLS). *Procedia Eng* . 2015, 125, 40–45.